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Supporting the Numeracy Development of Children with Additional Needs in Early Childhood Education in Ireland (From Birth to 7 Years)

A Review of the Literature

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Supporting the Numeracy Skill Development of Children with Special Educational Needs in Early Childhood Education in Ireland

(From birth to 7 years)

Sinéad McNally and Christina O’Keeffe

Overview

This report shares key findings and recommendations from a systematic review of the research literature to identify best practice and supports for the development of numeracy skills for young pupils with special educational needs in Early Childhood Education (birth to 7 years). The recommendations, identified from best international evidence, are for educators working with young children both in Early Childhood Education and Care settings (sometimes referred to as the Early Years’ sector and where the age range of children is from birth to age six) and in the infant classes in primary schools in Ireland (the age range of pupils is typically age four to seven). A systematic review of systematic reviews in the field of numeracy instruction for special educational needs in early childhood revealed that there were no systematic reviews on this topic in the past twenty years though several systematic reviews of older children sometimes included younger children in the study samples. Therefore, we conducted a full systematic review of the literature to identify original studies that investigated numeracy instruction and interventions for children with special educational needs in early childhood education. Nine studies met the inclusion criteria for this systematic review.

Research Questions

1. How can young children with special educational needs be supported in the development of numeracy skills in Early Childhood Education and Care settings and in the infant classes of primary schools (children aged birth to seven)?

Key Search Terms for a Systematic Review of Systematic Reviews of Numeracy Skills in Early Special Education

Target Skills / Learning:

Numeracy / arithmetic / problem solving / math fluency / number sense

Additional Learning Needs:

Special education / inclusive education / developmental disability / intellectual disability / Autism/Down Syndrome

Setting/Context:

Early childhood education / intervention / instruction / preschool

Type of Study**:

Systematic review / meta-analysis / research synthesis

Sample syntax with key words: ("numeracy" OR "math*" OR "arithmetic*" OR "problem solving" OR "math fluency" OR "number sense") AND ("intellectual disability*" OR "developmental disability" OR "cognitive disability*" OR "special education" OR "inclusive education") AND ("intervention" OR "instruction" OR "preschool") AND ("systematic review" OR "meta-analysis" OR "research synthesis")**

**This layer and Boolean string was excluded in our second systematic review which was a systematic review of the original studies on this topic.

Key Data Sources Consulted

Literature in the systematic review was from 2011 onwards with some reference to earlier seminal works. The search syntax was entered in the following databases (with amendments where necessary to match database requirements): SCOPUS, EBSCO (Academic Complete Search, ERIC, Education Complete Search, Education Index, PsychInfo and CINAHL) and Web of Science.

In addition to the systematic searches of the above databases, extensive hand searches were conducted on the reference lists of the most relevant systematic reviews, and on Google Scholar to identify articles and handbooks that did not appear in a systematic review, including 'Grey literature' such as reports published by international and national organisations, for example the NCCA and the NCSE.

A consistent search strategy was applied across databases. Boolean search strings were developed using keywords listed above and full syntax was written out before conducting the searches. A-priori inclusion criteria were developed in a protocol through collaborative discussions among the reports' authors before commencing the search process to identify potentially relevant studies. Covidence was used to facilitate the systematic reviews conducted and project records will be available for the systematic review reported here.

Tabulation of Results (please see appendix A)

Table 1. Table of studies found through a systematic search of the literature but which were excluded from the final synthesis as they did not fully meet inclusion criteria with regard to additional needs

Table 2. Data extraction for a systematic review of the literature on numeracy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education

Narrative Report

Introduction

This report focuses on identifying evidence-based numeracy supports in Early Childhood Education for children with additional needs. As outlined in our report on supporting the early literacy skills of children with additional needs, there have been shifts in educational policy towards inclusive education (IDEA, 1997; Griffin & Shevlin, 2011), with children with a range of additional needs increasingly taught in mainstream classrooms and settings in Ireland. The major policy context in Ireland is the 2004 Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs (EPSEN) Act (section 2) which specifies that children with special education needs should be educated, in so much as possible, within an inclusive classroom environment alongside peers who do not have such needs.

The quality of the ECE classroom instruction and environment is just as important as having access to mainstream and inclusive contexts. ECE in Ireland spans both Early Childhood Education and Care settings (birth to six years) which includes access to two universal preschool years (typically children are aged 3 to 5), and the junior and senior infant classrooms in primary schools. The early childhood curriculum, *Aistear*, is a play-based curriculum (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2009) which provides early childhood educators with a guide to quality practice to support early learning and development. Child-centred, the curriculum is informed by international research that recognises early childhood as an important period of development. Thus, for example emphasis is placed on the importance of environmental input and interactions from birth to three years which we know to be critical for establishing brain structures during this period of rapid brain development (Shonkoff & Philips, 2000). Situated within, and informed by, a bio-ecological perspective of development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), a growing body of Irish research indicates the importance of early caregiving input and contexts for children's learning and development (Williams, Greene, McNally, Murray & Quail, 2010; Williams, Murray, McCrory, & McNally, 2013; McGinnity, Russell & Murray, 2015).

Early Childhood Education and Numeracy Skill Development

With regard to numeracy and math skill development, early childhood education is seen as a crucial period for later mathematical outcomes (Duncan et al., 2007; Roberts & Bryant, 2011). Numeracy skills begin at an early age and three of the most commonly researched skills in preschool are numbering, numerical relations, and arithmetic operations (Purpura, 2009) as these are fundamental skills for later basic mathematics skills such as addition and subtraction (Purpura et al., 2011). Early numeracy is also sometimes referred to as early number sense (Root et al., 2020) and includes number recognition, counting, number patterns, number comparison, number operations, and estimation (Whitacre et al., 2017, in Root et al., 2020, p. 378).

Numeracy and mathematics in ECE are not synonymous terms and for the purposes of this report we focus on numeracy skills as defined by Davenport and her colleagues (2015):

Mathematics, specifically at the preschool level, includes the key components of number concepts, patterns and relationships, geometry, measurement, data collection, organization, and representation (Colker, Dodge, & Heroman, 2002). Numeracy, however, involves using mathematics in a more practical manner throughout our lives, including in our home, work, and community (Peters & Young- Loveridge, 2005). (p. 250)

We also draw on the Department of Education and Skills (2011) definition numeracy as similarly encompassing “[...] the ability to use mathematical understanding and skills to solve problems and meet the demands of day-to-day living in complex social settings” (p.8).

Though distinct domains, there are important links between literacy and numeracy skills in ECE. For example, there is support for embedding math content within stories as meaningful contexts help children to acquire this content (Cordova & Lepper, 1996). Further, David Purpura and his colleagues (2011) have found that discrete aspects of early literacy development, specifically vocabulary and print knowledge, uniquely predicted numeracy skills just before or at entry to school. Despite research on the ways in which both domains are important for later academic achievement (e.g. Duncan et al., 2007), numeracy for children in ECE has received less research attention than literacy development, with even less attention to teaching numeracy skills for children with *additional needs* in Early Childhood Education (Green et al., 2018). Given that children with disabilities and additional needs are more likely to have difficulties with number sense in early childhood (Titeca, Roeyers, Josephy, Ceulemans, & Desoete, 2014) and that number sense is foundational for later mathematics skills such as addition and subtraction (Purpura et al., 2011), this is a large and significant gap in the research literature and one that may have a substantial impact on special educational practice and policy.

Study Aims:

A Systematic Review of Numeracy Supports for Children with Additional Needs in ECE

To get an overview of the evidence base for numeracy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education (ECE), we conducted a systematic review of systematic reviews of numeracy supports for children with additional needs in ECE (from birth to eight years). We found no systematic review published in the past twenty years which met the inclusion criteria. While some systematic reviews focused on numeracy development of children with additional needs, these were for an older cohort of children and none focused on the Early Years, even where we broadened criteria to include reviews with a minimum of 50% of studies on the EYs and included those pre-2011. We therefore undertook a systematic review of the research literature with the search terms and syntax as outlined above. Our aim was to identify empirical studies that investigated educational supports or instruction for numeracy skill development for children with additional needs in early childhood (from birth to eight years).

A Note on Methodology

The search syntax was constructed such that systematic reviews and original research studies on (a) numeracy instruction for young children with (b) additional needs in (c) early childhood education could be identified. With regards to the first sphere or focus of the search syntax, a broad definition of numeracy was used, drawing on the definitions cited earlier. For the second sphere or focus of the search syntax, a broad and inclusive approach to ‘additional needs’ was used and included all children with an identifiable impairment, disability or delay. Studies were included only where children had been formally diagnosed or assessed. Studies which focused on numeracy instruction for young children with English as an additional language (EAL) were excluded from both systematic reviews unless the children also had a significant impairment or disability. This was done primarily because the literature on children with EAL indicates many ways in which the curriculum can be adapted to support bi/multilingual development (Bernardo, 2005; Han & Bridglall, 2009; NCCA, 2006; Saxe & Sussman, 2019). Finally, for the third sphere or focus of the search syntax, Early Years or ECE was defined as education from birth to eight years (the age at which almost all children in Ireland have completed senior infants).

Finally, in this report, we did not assess the risk of publication bias or include a quality appraisal of studies in the systematic review of the literature due to the heterogeneity of studies. However, we have provided, within the space constraints of table 2 detail on studies to allow readers to gauge the type and quality of study design, appropriateness of sampling, and types of findings

reported in light of targeted outcomes. Together these give an indication of the quality of the research in included studies without conducting a full quality appraisal.

Key Themes and Findings

Nine studies were included in the systematic review which met all inclusion criteria, i.e. all nine studies targeted early instruction, intervention or education for numeracy skill development for children with additional needs. Once again, findings are described according to a three-point classification system: positive, mixed or negative (see McNally & O’Keeffe review on literacy for special ECE in this series). Table 1 provides a list of studies that were found in the systematic search but that were excluded due to the type of numeracy difficulty identified (i.e. where children did not have a disability, delay or impairment that created an additional need in terms of special education provision or instruction). Themes and key findings based on the data extraction presented in table 2 are reported in narrative form here. Recommendations from narrative synthesis are highlighted following a short summary of the findings.

Study Characteristics

Additional Needs of Participants

Developmental Disability and Autism Spectrum Disorder were the two most commonly targeted additional needs in terms of numeracy intervention in the included studies. This is in line with reported prevalence rates within Irish schools (NCSE, 2016; 2017). Across all studies, participants ranged from 2-7 years, with a reported mean age of 4.64 years. Participants were predominantly boys (with the exception of Davenport & Johnston, 2015; Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Ingelin et al., 2020).

Instructional Approaches

Studies targeted a range of intervention approaches including e-books and stories for numeracy skills and direct instruction. Interventions drew on a range of methodologies including a large proportion of behavioural strategies which were developed from the extensive Early Intensive Behavioural Intervention literature (Davenport & Johnston, 2015; Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Ingelin et al., 2021; Mangundayao et al., 2013; Root et al., 2020). These included traditional behavioural components such as adult modelling (Ingelin et al., 2021; Root et al., 2020), prompting (Davenport & Johnston, 2015; Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Ingelin et al., 2021; Root et al., 2020), time

delay (Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Mangundayao et al., 2013), positive reinforcement (Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Mangundayao et al., 2013; Root et al., 2020), commands and directives (Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Mangundayao et al., 2013).

Four of the interventions were conducted by a researcher, three by preschool teachers trained in the intervention, and two studies did not specify who conducted the intervention. This is important to note when assessing the potential for generalising effectiveness of these instructional techniques to ECE settings and classrooms. Despite calls for collaboration between parents/caregivers and schools in supporting early numeracy development (NEPS, 2020), few studies incorporated parent/caregiver input as part of a collaborative approach.

Location, Context and Implementation

Seven of the nine studies which met the inclusion criteria were conducted in the USA and two in Israel. The majority of studies were implemented within preschool settings (n=6) with one study implemented in a special kindergarten class for children with ASD (with the exception of Segal-Drori et al., 2019 and Shamir & Baruch 2012 who do not specify intervention setting). Most of these settings (n=4) involved inclusive classrooms, comprising of children with disabilities and typically developing peers with three studies focusing on special classrooms for children with disabilities. Furthermore, four out of these 7 studies conducted within school settings, incorporated interventions as part of classroom activities (Davenport & Johnston, 2015; Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Odom et al., 2019; Root et al., 2020). This is of particular importance given the drive for inclusive class supports (Finkelstein et al., 2021; Florian, 2015; Lindner & Schwab, 2020; Lingo et al., 2011; Molbaek, 2017).

Frequency of interventions ranged from twice daily to three-times weekly, with the majority of interventions implemented daily (with the exception of Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019, Segal-Drori et al., 2019, Shamir & Baruch 2012 who do not specify intervention details). The intensity of interventions ranged from 5 to 25 minutes (with the exception of Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019 and Odom et al., 2019 who do not specify intensity) with an average delivery of 15 minutes; there was much variability surrounding the duration of interventions given that the majority implemented single-subject experimental designs and varied across participants.

Given the dearth of early childhood numeracy research for children with additional needs, we imposed no restrictions in the inclusion criteria regarding research design except for single case study designs which were excluded due to the lack of generalisability of findings. As can be seen in table 2, just over half of the studies (five) are single-subject experimental designs which limit the generalisability of findings to larger populations though the effectiveness of the intervention on

specific participants can be reliably assessed (Janosky, 2005). Three of the remaining studies were quasi-experimental designs involving at least one condition and a control group, and one study was a crossover randomized controlled trial of an integrated curriculum model.

E-Books and Stories for Numeracy Skills for Children with Additional Needs in ECE

Three (Green et al., 2018; Segal-Driori et al., 2019; Shamir & Baruch, 2012) of the nine studies included in this systematic review focused on a form of storytelling for the development of numeracy skills for children with additional needs. These interventions involved integration of literacy and numeracy which, given challenges around curriculum overload and increasing demands/time pressures experienced by teachers (Majoni, 2017; NCCA, 2010; OECD, 2020), may be of particular importance for practice in education. Incidentally, these studies were the three quasi-experimental design studies and involved at least one intervention condition and a control group, and all three focused on developmental delay which poses a significant risk for Learning Disability. These similarities allow for some comparability in design and target sample. However, the intervention varied with both Segal-Driori et al. (2019) and Shamir and Baruch (2012) focusing on e-book interventions for similar target numeracy skills (e.g. essence of addition and conceptualisation of ordinal numbers) while Green et al. (2018) focused on shared story book reading with a mathematics focus and related activities. Shamir is an author on both e-book studies so there is a strong link in the development of both 2012 and 2019 studies. The focus is on children's use of e-books independently to learn math concepts using e-books with a variety of modes or settings (e.g. 'read only' mode to avoid distraction or more interactive modes to explore difficult words). Both studies reported significant improvement for children with additional needs on essence of addition and conceptualisation of ordinal numbers which contributes to the limited literature on the use of e-books as a classroom technology and support for numeracy skill development for young children at risk of Learning Disability.

Green et al.'s (2018) study takes a much more interactive focus in their intervention which comprised shared reading with mathematical content included through scripted questioning and discussions as well as story-related mathematical activities after the reading of the story. Focusing on number and operations they sought to teach "number sense and the understanding of whole numbers, concepts of correspondence, counting, cardinality, and comparison" (p. 3) through a common preschool practice, namely shared reading. They found significant positive outcomes in terms of children's overall math skills and three measures of number sense, namely, quantity comparison, one-to-one correspondence counting, and oral counting. However, this intervention was implemented by the researcher and in self-contained special education preschool classrooms, highlighting the need for

further research on the feasibility of implementing this intervention in mainstream inclusive settings and by educators rather than researchers.

Direct Instruction for Numeracy Skills for Children with Additional Needs in ECE

Several studies highlighted that direct instruction of several numeracy skills is likely to be more effective for many children with additional needs (e.g. Davenport & Johnston, 2015; Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown, 2019; Root et al., 2020). This corresponds with national guidance (NEPS, 2020) and broader literature recommendations (Gersten et al., 2009; King et al., 2016; Spooner et al., 2019). Davenport and Johnston (2015), for example, implemented most-to-least prompting embedded during ongoing inclusive classroom activities by early childhood teachers. Similarly, Hawkins-Lear and Grisham-Brown (2019) employed systematic teaching strategies including constant time delay that was also embedded during ongoing classroom activities in the form of individual and group play sessions. Finally, Root et al. (2020) incorporated explicit instruction during math centre time activities based on modelling, prompts and praise in supporting number sense skills. Each of these studies demonstrated positive findings throughout for all participants (with ASD/DD) regarding improvements in targeted early numeracy skills. Mangundayao et al. (2013) examined the impact of a direct instruction flashcard system on colour, shape and number identification of children with developmental delay with mixed results.

Ingelin et al. (2021), on the other hand, demonstrated positive outcomes for three participants' (with ASD) on number sense skills based on the incorporation of both explicit and implicit teaching approaches. Implicit techniques involved a socio-constructivist approach to learning which were grounded in discussions between children with ASD and typically developing peers within small groups, facilitated by the instructor. Explicit techniques included a system of least prompts and modelling.

Odom et al. (2019) employed an integrated curriculum in supporting academic skills of children with multiple disabilities. Mathematical curricular activities were not found to be effective for children with a range of additional needs and disabilities with authors concluding that instructional approaches required greater level of adaptation based on children's needs/learning style, as reflected within the wider literature (NEPS, 2020).

Three studies targeted the number sense skills specifically of young children with ASD (Hawkins-Lear and Grisham-Brown, 2019; Ingelin et al., 2021; Root et al., 2020). All three were single-subject experimental designs and all reported positive findings for children with ASD which is in keeping with the large volume of literature on direct instruction for young children with ASD.

Summary

Our systematic review of the research literature found a large and significant gap in empirical research on teaching numeracy skills for young children with additional needs in the past ten years, and this is in keeping with findings from other researchers. While it is challenging to determine clear recommendations on a limited research base that includes different designs and children with very different additional needs, the studies included a rich and well described study of shared reading for early numeracy development for children with developmental delay (Davenport and Johnston, 2015) as well as early support for the effective use of e-books to engage children with developmental delays to learn the essence of addition and enhance the conceptualisation of ordinal numbers (e.g. Shamir et al., 2012).

Direct instruction on discrete numeracy skills was also a positive strategy which is unsurprising given the large literature on single-subject experimental designs for children with ASD and other additional needs. Indeed, the only study which did not report positive outcomes for children with additional needs was a large scale study of an integrated curriculum (Odom et al., 2019). A third of studies focused on number sense for children with ASD, all of which were direct instruction strategies.

The new primary mathematics curriculum under development places an importance on learning mathematics and numeracy skills through playful experiences in the early childhood education classrooms. Given the dearth of research on teaching numeracy skills for young children with additional needs, and especially in mainstream inclusive contexts, it is not surprising that there is also a lack of research on teaching numeracy through play and interactive experiences for young children in special early childhood education. This is an important gap in our knowledge base and future research is needed which can assess the potential impact of playful learning opportunities for numeracy skill development for all children in ECE settings.

This systematic review further highlights the importance of considering children's characteristics and type of additional need(s), as well as the intervention context for delivery of instruction. It also highlights the lack of research implemented by educators in the classroom: it is critical that future research on numeracy skill supports for children with additional needs in ECE actively involves educators in delivery of the strategies which are the focus of the research to ensure generalisability to classroom practice.

Recommendations

All recommendations are tentative except for those that specify the need for further research. This is due to the small number of studies published on this topic in the past ten years and the proportion of studies which used a single-subject experimental design. As discussed earlier in this report, these designs allow for conclusions to be drawn about the effectiveness of a programme or intervention for specific participants but do not easily allow for generalisation to larger populations especially where few studies are reported in a field. We join other researchers in special Early Childhood Education (e.g. Green included in this review) in highlighting the lack of research on children with additional needs with regard to numeracy skills and emphasise the significance of this gap in light of the importance of numeracy skill development at entry to school for later academic success (Claessens, Duncan, & Engel, 2009). The recommendations which can be made on the basis of this limited literature include:

1. Shared reading with a focus on teaching key numeracy skills is a promising strategy for supporting numeracy for children with additional needs and fits with previous literature on the importance of oral language in numeracy skill development. Shared reading is also a well-established and common activity in ECE classrooms with a growing literature supporting the use of literature as a context for numeracy skill development. Though research is limited it is likely that shared reading can offer positive educational opportunities in numeracy skills for all children including those with additional needs (pillar 5).
2. E-books similarly may be an engaging format for children with developmental delays who are at-risk of Learning Disability in which to support numeracy development and this also fits with emerging literature around the effectiveness of digital formats for shared reading that we saw with regard to literacy skill development for young children with additional needs (pillar 5).
3. Explicit approaches and direct instruction to teach discrete skills are likely to be effective in the context of a behavioural or applied behaviour analysis approach to instruction. Research often includes the researcher as the interventionist given the specific training required for these approaches, and more research is needed where educators are the interventionist to allow for greater understanding as to what may be the most effective and practical strategies for supporting all children in inclusive ECE (pillar 5).
4. Research is required that investigates the potential effectiveness of strategies that incorporate numeracy skill development in playful interactions and learning opportunities in inclusive classroom contexts for children with additional needs. This is especially important given the

emphasis placed on the importance of playful learning contexts for the numeracy skills in early childhood education curricula.

5. Finally, as with literacy skill development in ECE, we strongly recommend a systematic review of research on children with specific additional needs (e.g. ASD, Learning Disability) is undertaken, and the evidence base is regularly updated, given the significant heterogeneity among children (pillar 5).

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Short biographical notes

Dr Sinéad McNally is a developmental psychologist at the DCU Institute of Education. Her published research investigates children's early language and learning through play and reading, including a special focus on the development of young autistic children in educational contexts. Sinéad is lead Principal Investigator of an interdisciplinary study on the educational experiences of autistic pupils in primary and secondary schools in Ireland. Funded by a COALESCE award from the Irish Research Council, this is the first large-scale systematic study on the experiences of autistic pupils in Ireland. For her research on children's early language and literacy development, Sinéad has been awarded faculty fellowships at Boston University and at the DCU Institute of Education, and funding awards

from Science Foundation Ireland, the Standing Conference on Teacher Education North and South, and the European Consortium of Innovative Universities. She teaches research methods and child development to pre-service early childhood educators and leads a team of early career researchers at the School of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education.

Ms Christina O’Keeffe

Christina O’Keeffe is an Assistant Professor at the School of Inclusive and Special Education at the DCU Institute of Education. Christina holds a Bachelor of Education and Psychology and Graduate Diploma in Special Education Needs from Mary Immaculate College (MIC). The majority of her teaching career has focused on supporting autistic children within early childhood education. Christina is currently undertaking a research PhD scholarship, funded by Dublin City University’s Educational Trust, based on the role of play for inclusion within early childhood education. Her published research on the role of play in Early Childhood Education for the inclusion of young autistic children highlights the importance of play in special education.

Table 1. Table of studies found through a systematic search of the literature on numeracy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education: includes studies where children were at risk/not necessarily disability and did not meet inclusion criteria

Reference	Age (as reported by authors in years and/or months)	Professional Diagnosis	Instructional Approach/Intervention	Numeracy Outcomes	Findings
Hardy & Hemmeter (2021) USA	48-54 months; M=51 months	Children at risk of mathematical difficulties (recognised by teachers)	Systematic modelling with mathematical language and a prompting procedure	Individualised Targets; 1) Sorting by size; 2) Putting numerals 1-5 in order; 3) Duplicating AB Pattern; 4) Matching shapes to pictures; 5) Counting up to 5 objects; 6) Sorting by colour	Mixed
Hinton et al. (2016) USA	5 years, M= 5 years	Children at risk of mathematical difficulties (recognised by teachers)	Explicit Counting Intervention	Resultative Counting; Shortened Counting; Graphic Counting	Mixed
Praet & Desoete (2019) Belgium	NS; M=68.41	Children experiencing learning problems as indicated by percentile scores	Educational Math Games	Early Numeracy Skills; 1) Procedural Counting Knowledge; 2) Conceptual Counting Knowledge; 3) Calculation Tasks, as measured by TED-MATH	Positive
Salminen et al. (2015) Finland	Kindergarten (age not specified)	Children at risk of mathematical difficulties and scoring at or below 10th percentile in tests of verbal counting (recognised by teachers)	Computer-Assisted Intervention; GraphoGame Math and Number Race Software Programs	Early Number Skills: Verbal Counting; Object Counting; Basic Arithmetic	Mixed
Shanley et al. (2021) USA	NS; M=5.2 years	Children with ELL; Children eligible for free lunch; Children undergoing special education services	ROOTS Intervention	RAENS; counting and cardinality, number operations, and the base-10 system TEMA-3; conceptual and procedural understanding of math, including counting and basic calculations Stanford Achievement Test—10th Edition; Problem Solving and Procedures	Mixed
Sood et al. (2013) USA	56-80 months, M=66.36	Children with ELL; Children eligible for free lunch; Children undergoing special education services	Early Number Sense Intervention	Counting and Number Identification; 1) oral counting fluency; 2) counting from; 3) number identification Number sense—Number relationships: 1) spatial relationships; 2) more and less relationships; 3) five and ten benchmarks; 4) nonverbal calculation	Positive
Watts et al. (2020) USA	5.0-5.5 years; M=5.26 years	Children at risk of mathematical difficulties based on mathematical performance (identified by teachers)	Number Line Board-Game Intervention involving cross-age peer tutors with EBD	TEMA-3; numbering skills, number comparison facility, calculation skills, and understanding of concepts; numerical literacy, mastery of number facts, calculation skills, and understanding of concepts TEMI-AC; magnitude comparisons, number identification, number sequences, and quantity recognition	Positive

Table 2. Data extraction for a systematic review of the literature on numeracy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education

Author, Year, Country	Sample Characteristics				Methodology	Name	Intervention Components	Frequency, Intensity, Duration	Interventionist	Setting /Context	Target Literacy Outcomes	Results
	Number	Age (as reported by authors in years and/or months)	Gender	Professional Diagnosis								
Davenport & Johnston (2015) USA	3 children with disabilities	4.2-4.9 years; M=4.6years	1 Male; 2 Female	Developmental Delay and Chiari Malformation (N=1); Developmental Delay, Cerebral Palsy and Seizure Disorder (N=1); Developmental Delay, Seizure Disorder and Hypotonia (N=1)	Single-subject Experimental Design	Most-Least Prompting and Contingent Consequences	Intervention embedded opportunities to teach identified skill e.g. building tower with number symbols, decorating shakers with identified shapes. Researcher prompted desired behaviour (presented verbal task demand and implemented most-to-least prompting) and provided consequences in the form of verbal feedback and natural consequences as part of activities	1-2 times Daily; 5-15 minutes; Duration varied for each participant from 29-32 days	Researcher	Public and Inclusive Preschool Classroom (N=3); Daily free choice time (learning centres)	Individualised numeracy targets (Point to number symbols 2,3,4; Point to number symbols 6,7,9; Point to shapes including diamond, rectangle and triangle). Criterion for mastery were defined as 4/5 unprompted correct responses across three consecutive days	Positive; All three participants increased targeted areas of numeracy skills from baseline to intervention
Green et al. (2018) USA	50 children with disabilities (24 treatment group; 26 comparison group)	3-5years; M=25 months (Treatment group 24 months)	17 Male; 7 Female (Overall total=39 Male; 11 Female)	Developmental Delay	Quasi-Experimental Design	Shared storybook reading intervention with related math activities	Intervention group engaged in storybook reading and math instruction related to the storybook. Children in the comparison group received a 10-min storybook reading. Researcher-created scripted questions and elaborations were used throughout the storybook. The intervention small groups were provided with (a) a review of math concepts from the prior session, (b) shared storybook reading by the PI or the intervention research assistant with guided math questions and elaborations, and (c) one small group math activity as directed on the lesson plans through an explicit and direct instruction model. Each session closed with a review of comprehension and math concepts from the story	Three times weekly; 20-minute sessions; 6 weeks	Researcher	Self-Contained Preschool Classrooms for children with special needs (N=10); NS	Total Math Ability, as measured in TEMA-3 Number sense skills: Quantity Comparison; 1-1 Correspondence counting; Oral Counting, as measured in IGDIS-EN	Positive; Intervention group demonstrated significant improvement in total math ability as well as all three number sense skills
Hawkins-Lear & Grisham-Brown (2019) USA	4 children with disabilities	3-5 years M=4.25 years	2 Male; 2 Female	Autism Spectrum Disorder (N=2); Developmental Delay (N=2)	Single-subject Experimental Design	Embedding Constant Time-delay teaching strategy into classroom activities and routines	During intervention, a minimum of 4 instructional trials were delivered in the context of 1-1 play activities and an additional 4 delivered during small group instructional activities using CTD. 1-1 play activities were altered depending on target skill (e.g. counting markers, crayons, manipulatives; playing with small and large cups in dramatic play; playing with short and long blocks) as well as small group activities (counting crayons and markers with peers; talking about small and large flowers; painting with long and short paintbrushes)	NS	Trained preschool teachers (N=2)	Preschool; Inclusive classrooms (n=2); 1-1 Play and Small Group activities	Acquisition of number sense individualised for each participant e.g. counting objects, identification of size concepts (big and small; long and short) with 100% accuracy across two activities over 3 consecutive days	Positive; All four participants demonstrated an increase in criterion from baseline to post-intervention
Ingein et al. (2021) USA	11 children (3 with ASD and 8 typically developing peers)	4.4-4.11 years; M=4.34 years	1 Male; 2 Female	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Single-subject Experimental Design	Adapted Number Talks Intervention	Each session consisted of 3-dot images design presented on an iPad. Followed same procedures as Number Talks Intervention with the addition of visual supports, modelling of strategies and system of least prompts. Steps included: 1) Children sat at a small table clear of items; 2) Researcher showed dot image on iPad; 3) Children determined the number of dots and indicated when they were ready to share using thumbs-up; 4) Children shared how many dots by verbally naming or pointing to picture (using system of least prompts as needed); 5) Teacher models effective strategies; 6) Researcher helped all children compare answers to reach consensus; 7) Repeat steps for each 3-dot pattern	Three times weekly; 15-20 minutes; Duration varied for each participant based on mastery levels	Researcher	Preschool; Inclusive Classroom (N=2); Quiet area outside of classroom (therapy room and hallway); Small groups including 1 child with ASD and 2-3 typically developing peers	Number Sense Skills: Percentage of correct answers on number sense probe based on recognition of numbers, parts of numbers and subitize	Positive; All three students increased scores on probe from baseline to intervention
Mangundayao et al. (2013) USA	3 children	4-5 years; M=4.3 years	2 Male; 1 Female	Developmental Delay	Single-subject Experimental Design	Direct Instructions Flashcard System	Three sets of flashcards were created: colours, shapes and numerals. During the DI Flashcard System, the participants were presented with the flashcard and asked to identify the item presented. If the student correctly identified the item, the author indicated the answer	NS; 3-7 minutes; Duration	Researcher	Public elementary school; Special pre-school	Number of Correctly Identified Colours, Shapes and Numerals	Mixed; Only one participant gained mastery across all three sets (colours, shapes and numerals) with other two

							on the data collection sheet and presented the participant with an M&M. If the participants incorrectly identified the item presented, a model, test procedure was used to teach the skill.	varied for each participant		classroom; work area of classroom with erected boundaries to reduce distraction		children reaching mastery across one set
Odum et al. (2019) USA	1,117 children (737 children at risk due to poverty; 210 ELL; 171 identified disability)	NS; M=54 months	603 Male; 514 Female	ADHD (N=11); ASD (N=5); EBD (N=7); Developmental Delay (N=28); Learning Disability (N=3); Physical Disability (N=4); Speech/Language Disorder (N=68); Visual Impairment (N=6); Other health impairment (N=5); Other (N=13); Not specified (N=21)	Crossover Randomised Controlled Trial	Children's School Success Curriculum	Curriculum model that integrated content for literacy, math, science, and social domains The daily lessons included large group activities, small group activities, plans for extending discussion of themes across the day, and procedures for individualization. Content for daily math activities was drawn from the Building Blocks curriculum and the professional literature. The curricular goals focused on teaching beginning numbers and operations, geometry and spatial sense, measurement, pattern/algebraic thinking, and displaying and analysing data. Small group math activities occurred every day and also were often integrated into the science component.	Daily; NS; Total 133 lessons over 5-year period	Trained preschool teachers (N=10)	Inclusive preschool classrooms; Small group activities	Math composite variable scores from two sub-tests of Woodcock-Johnson (Applied Problem and Quantitative Concepts)	Negative: Intervention group demonstrated significantly more skills on average in comparison to control group however no significant treatment differences were reported for group with identified disabilities
Root et al. (2020) USA	3 children with ASD	6 years; M=6 years	3 Male	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Single-subject Experimental Design	Early Numeracy Curriculum	Implemented all four thematic units of Early Numeracy Curriculum (each addresses 7 early numeracy domains including counting, sets, symbol use, patterns, measurement, calendar, numeral identification). Teacher began each lesson by reading thematic story, then re-read story and followed scripted lesson to use explicit instruction to first model target skills and then asked students to perform skills independently using a system of least prompts to assist	Daily; 10 minutes 4 months	Trained Preschool Teacher (n=1)	Private Special School (ASD); Early Kindergarten Classroom; 1-1 instruction time during maths centres	Early Number Sense Skills; measured by performance on EN-A test from Early Numeracy Curriculum	Positive; All three children demonstrated increase in early number sense skills from baseline to intervention
Segal-Drori et al. (2019) Israel	107 children (56 typically developing peers; 51 children at risk learning disability)	4.6-7 years; M= 5.78 years	34 Male; 17 Female	Developmental Delay	Quasi-Experimental	Electronic Storybook with Math Content	Two groups of kindergarteners were randomly divided into two subgroups; an intervention group in which the children engaged in the educational e-book activity, and a control group in which the children participated in the regular kindergarten program, without the e-book intervention	NS; 25 minutes; Total 5 sessions	NS	NS	Essence of Addition; Comprised of two concepts; 'more' and 'how much more' based on subtest MAMTA Conceptualisation of ordinal numbers test involving series of pictures of animals standing in row based on MAMTA	Positive: Intervention group demonstrated significant improvement in measures of 'essence of addition' and 'ordinal numbers'
Shamir & Baruch (2012) Israel	77 children with developmental delay	4.5-7.0 years M=5.88 years	56 Male; 21 Female	Developmental Delay/disability	Quasi-experimental	Educational Electronic Book with/without metacognitive guidance	Participants were randomly assigned to one of three groups: 1) intervention sessions with educational e-book and metacognitive guidance (in the form of instructions spoken by narrator); 2) intervention sessions with educational e-book without metacognitive guidance; 3) Control group who participated in regular kindergarten activities. Both e-book sessions involved three modes: 1) Read story online; 2) Read and play with numbers; 3) Read and play while rhyming	NS; 20 minutes; Total 6 sessions	NS	NS	Essence of Addition; Comprised of two concepts; 'more' and 'how much more' based on subtest MAMTA Conceptualisation of ordinal numbers test involving series of pictures of animals standing in row and four sub-tests of MAMTA involving position, accurate meaning, direction and sequence	Positive; Significant difference in results on essence of addition between both intervention groups and control group. No significant difference reported between intervention groups Significant difference in results on ordinal numbers between both intervention groups and control group. No significant difference between intervention groups

NS=Not Specified